

THE CONSTITUTIVE FLOW BEHAVIOR OF 6061Al-SiC_p COMPOSITES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the studies on plastic deformation of SiC particle reinforced Al6061 alloy matrix composites at elevated temperature and its comparison with that of fiber/whisker reinforced composites. Hot deformation tests were carried out on Al6061-18vol.%SiC_p composites and the flow stress curves were developed as a function of temperature and strain rate. The steady-state flow was found to be the main feature of the true stress versus true strain curves in all the cases. The apparent activation energy for hot deformation of MMC was calculated to be three times as high as the activation energy for self-diffusion in aluminium. No evidence of strain hardening was observed at higher strains (0.05 to 0.5) unlike in the case of fiber reinforced MMCs. This is possibly due to the relatively faster diffusional relaxation in particle reinforced composites.

Keywords: Aluminium matrix composite, plastic deformation, diffusion, relaxation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the deformation behaviour of aluminium matrix composites at elevated temperature is receiving great deal of attention [1-3] because of its importance from the point of view of use of these composites in creep resistant applications and also from the point of view of forming into net shape components by secondary forming processes. In a number of studies, it has been noted that flow stress values and the rate of strain hardening are sensitive to the imposed strain rate and the test temperature. Different relaxation processes have been identified in the last two decades by several investigators both for particle [4-6] and fiber reinforced MMCs [7,8]. The principal relaxation mechanisms are dislocation glide and diffusional relaxation. Thus the kinetics of stress relaxation is the key factor in determining elevated temperature mechanical properties. It has been reported that interface diffusion should dominate in a material having fine inclusions at low temperature, whereas at elevated temperature bulk diffusion should dominate in materials having large size inclusions. At high temperature it is possible for the dislocations to accumulate at the particles and climb out, especially in high stacking fault energy (SFE) materials. If the rate of climb at the particle is greater than the rate of dislocation accumulation then there will be no strain hardening in the material. Stanford-Beale and Clyne [9] have reported work hardening of δ -Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced 6061Al composite at elevated temperatures beyond a critical strain rate.

In the present paper the constitutive flow behaviour of 6061Al-SiC_p MMCs has been studied using kinetic approach. Arrhenius type rate equation [10] was used to analyze the deformation kinetics. In this study an attempt has been made to compare our results with previously published results. A model has been developed to validate the experimental results and to differentiate the operating mechanisms of stress relaxations in particle and fiber reinforced composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The chemical composition of the 6061 Al alloy used in the present study, in weight percent, is 1.7 Mg, 0.6 Si, 0.3 Cu, 0.23 Fe, 0.2 Mn, 0.22 other elements and rest aluminium. SiC particles (SiC_p) of average size 40 micrometer and of aspect ratio 1-2 were used as reinforcement. The bulk of work reported here is based on 18 vol% SiC_p - 6061Al composite materials made by casting route. Cast billets were subjected to hot extrusion at a temperature of 520°C with an extrusion ratio of 12:1.

Figure 1. The initial microstructure of 18vol.%SiC_p-Al6061 composite material

Figure 1 shows the initial microstructure of the MMC. Hot compression tests were carried out on specimens of height 15mm and diameter of 10mm within a temperature range of 300°C to 552°C and with a constant strain rate in the range of 0.001s⁻¹ to 1.0s⁻¹. In each case, the specimen was deformed to half its height (50% strain). A computer-controlled servohydraulic testing machine (DARTEC, U.K.) was used to carry out the tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flow Behaviour

No evidence of flow softening was found in all the cases, but the variation of flow stress during a test was found to be a strong function of imposed strain rate and temperature. Only a limited strain hardening was observed upto a strain of 0.05 in all the cases, which is followed by a distinct steady-state region upto a strain of 0.5. Table 1 exhibits the variation of true stress with temperature and strain rate at a strain of 0.5. Increase in true stress with decreasing temperature is significant at a constant strain rate.

Figure 2 illustrates the variation of true stress with temperature at different imposed strain rates. The observed dependence of flow stress of 6061Al-SiC_p on strain rate has been shown in Figure 3 which has been superimposed with Stanford-Beale and Clyne's [9] results reported for δ-Al₂O₃-6061Al composite materials at three different temperatures. They report a sharp increase in flow stress beyond a critical strain rate due to high work hardening rate even at elevated temperatures. Strain rate sensitivity (m), a parameter that correlates the concepts of dislocation with that of macroscopic mechanical behaviour, has been calculated from the slope of each straight line when log of flow stress is plotted against log of strain rate at different temperatures. Stress exponent (n)

has been calculated from the strain rate sensitivity ($n=1/m$) for the same material at a strain of 0.3. Figure 4 shows the variation of stress exponent with temperature. The value of 'n' for the composite ranges from 9.09 at 300°C to 4.34 at 550°C, which are significantly higher than that of unreinforced alloy ($n \approx 3-4$). Similarly, in a creep study Part et al. [11] found it to be as high as 25 for 30.0 vol.%SiC-6061Al composites within a temperature range of 345°C to 405°C. Nieh [12] reported a value of 21 for 17.4 vol.%SiC-6061Al composites within a temperature range of 232°C to 371°C. The next part^w of the investigation is aimed at understanding the presence of any threshold value and its effect on the stress exponent.

Table 1 True stress values (in MPa) at a strain of 0.5

$\dot{\epsilon}$ (s^{-1})	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)					
	300	350	400	450	500	550
0.001	54.80	41.20	26.00	20.20	12.70	6.70
0.01	72.00	54.30	39.30	24.75	19.70	13.40
0.1	100.00	70.00	57.70	41.00	30.00	20.30
1.0	115.00	96.40	80.00	56.25	41.00	30.70

Figure 2 Variation of true stress with temperature as a function of strain rate

Figure 3 Dependence of flow stress of fiber/whisker [9] and particle reinforced composites on strain rate

3.2 Apparent Activation Energy Determination

An Arrhenius type rate equation [10] has been used to find out apparent activation energy of hot deformation. Although experiments have reported that there is no unique activation energy over the whole temperature range for monolithic materials, Arrhenius type rate equation gives fairly good approximation. The relation is given by

$$\dot{\epsilon} = B\sigma^n \exp(-Q_H/RT) \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the constant strain rate, σ is the true stress, n is the stress exponent, Q_H is the apparent activation energy, T is the test temperature in absolute scale, R is the universal gas constant and B is a constant. Using the value of 'n' the apparent activation energy is estimated from the slopes of $\ln \ln(\sigma)$ versus $(1/T)$ plots, Figure 5, and compared with apparent activation energy reported by Nieh [22] and Park et al. [11] from their creep studies (Table 2). The present study indi-

cates that the stress exponent is significantly high and varies remarkably with temperature. The experimentally measured activation energy has been found to be 422 ± 5 KJ/mol which is almost three times as high as the activation energy for self-diffusion in aluminium (142KJ/mol).

Table 2 Experimental activation energy values from creep studies [11,12]

Material	Temp. (°C)	Activation Energy (KJ/mol)
30.0v %SiC -6061Al [11]	345-405	270-500
17.4v %SiC _w ^p -6061Al [12]	232-371	391

Figure 4 Variation of stress exponent (n) with temperature

Figure 5 Arrhenius plot for 18vol.%SiC - Al6061 composite at a strain of 0.3

3.3 Degradation of Microstructures

It has been noticed that the degree of fiber fracture during the test was greater for those conditions which lead to higher flow stress values [9]. At higher strain rate severe fiber fracture occurred and final aspect ratio of fibers was reduced to as low as 8-9 from an initial aspect ratio of about 50. Whereas, for low strain rate the final aspect ratio remained relatively high (20-25) after experiencing similar strain. The average principal shear stress experienced by the δ -Al₂O₃ fiber can be calculated and compared with that required for fiber fracture. To obtain a lower bound for the principal stress (τ) the following relation [13] can be used

$$\tau = \mu f \gamma \quad (2)$$

where μ is the shear modulus of the matrix, f is the volume fraction of the fibers and γ is the shear strain. An upper bound is obtained when the resulting shear stress is larger by a factor of only $(1+\nu)$, where ν is the Poisson's ratio of the fiber. It has been found that it is acceptable upto a strain of 25% for Cu-SiO₂ system. The larger the strain, the higher the level of accumulated stress. Shear within the fiber or decohesion at the fiber-matrix interface at any stage of the deformation process can occur if the local stress exceeds that required to cause failure. For 18 vol.% δ -Al₂O₃-6061Al composite, at shear strains of 0.25 and 0.75, the principal stresses are found to be 0.045μ GPa and 0.135μ GPa, respectively. The principal stresses exceed the fracture stress of δ -Al₂O₃ fiber i.e, about 1.2 GPa [14], even when the shear modulus of the matrix is as low as 27.0 GPa and 9.0 GPa, respectively.

Thus there is a possibility of fiber damage (fiber fracture or interface decohesion) even during elevated temperature compression test which is in good agreement with the results reported by Stanford-Beale and Clyne [9].

Unlike fiber reinforced composites, SiC particle reinforced composites do not show any evidence of work hardening within the given range of strain rates ($1.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at 552°C . Moreover, particle fracture was not observed after elevated temperature compression tests.

3.4 Stress Relaxation Phenomenon

Although contributions of different strengthening mechanisms, such as internal stress, grain and subgrain hardening, solute and precipitation hardening are quite significant at low temperatures, however, most of these are expected to contribute to a lesser degree at elevated temperature. Dislocation-particle interactions and dislocation-dislocation interactions are considered to be more important factors at elevated temperature. Under the influence of thermal as well as mechanical loading, different restoration mechanisms can play important roles due to high thermal diffusion. Although, at the present moment, limited literature is available on the mechanism of stress relaxation, it can be developed from the existing models, either from the relaxation-time determination method [8] or from climb rate determination method [15].

Here, an attempt has been made to develop a model based on climb rate determination. The rate of dislocation accumulation (dn/dt) has been determined using a relation, originally proposed by Ashby [13] and subsequently modified for high SFE materials undergoing deformation at elevated temperature. A term, P_r , which takes care of the elimination of dislocations from the pile-up, has been included in the original relation i.e.,

$$dn/dt = 2 \dot{\epsilon} d P_r / b \quad (3)$$

where P_r is the probability of elimination of dislocations by climb from the pile-up and the final expression takes the form

$$dn/dt = 2 \dot{\epsilon} d \exp(-Q/RT) / b \quad (4)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the imposed strain rate, d is the average size of the particle, Q is the activation energy for climb, b is the Burgers vector and T is the test temperature in absolute scale. With proper choice of values the rate of dislocation accumulation is calculated to be nearly 8 dislocations/second.

Since, the rate of recovery of dislocations (dL/dt) at the particles depends primarily on the line tension of dislocations and high thermal diffusion of vacancies, an equation of the following type has been applied [16]

$$dL/dt = 2 \Pi a D \sqrt{\mu} / r d^2 K T \quad (5)$$

where a is the atomic volume, D is the thermal diffusivity, μ is the shear modulus, r is the radius of the loop at any instant, d is the average size of the particles, K is the Boltzman constant and T is the test temperature in absolute scale. The rate of removal of dislocations by climb is calculated to be 409 dislocations/second under similar conditions of test temperature and imposed strain rate.

It implies that strain hardening is likely to be absent in the particle composite materials, because of faster relaxation of stress by the process of climb at the particles. However, this is not true for fiber reinforced composites, since the diffusion path is of the order of the fiber length [9]. The difference between the mechanisms of climb at the particles and whiskers lies in the fact that the climb of

dislocations at particles is aided both by the line tension and thermal diffusion, whereas in case of fibers climb is only aided by thermal diffusion. So climb of dislocations at the particles is expected to be much faster than that of fibers and this is attributed to the absence of strain hardening in the particle composites materials.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The constitutive flow behaviour of 18vol.%SiC-6061Al composite materials is strongly temperature and strain rate dependent. There is no evidence of strain hardening in particle composite beyond a plastic strain of 0.05 unlike fiber composites which display strain hardening during elevated temperature uniaxial compression tests. Both the stress exponent and apparent activation energy for hot deformation are higher for particle composite materials than that of unreinforced alloy. The absence of strain hardening in particle composite is attributed to relatively faster plastic relaxation than that of fiber composite materials.

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